

Data Compression

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1 Problem

In a network with a number of low-power devices like sensor nodes which have constrained memory, how can you fit code and data which is greater in size than the available memory in the most energy-efficient manner? Sensor networks are typically employed to achieve distributed micro sensing: a collection of small sensor nodes coordinate to leverage their individual sensor tasks into a larger task. Their individual computation capability is trivial and limited by their battery power levels. One of the requirements of data transfer here is that the basic functionality of the network should not be hindered in any possible manner. For example, data should be routed from the source to the destination successfully without consuming too many resources of this network. Also, in some scenarios with mission-critical applications, communication should happen as quickly as possible. We cannot use restrictive data structures here as we do not want to reduce functionality (or to lose information) in any way.

2 Context

A sensor network [1] consists of sensor nodes (typically called as ‘motes’) which are individually capable of performing small tasks and are distributed spatially in the work-field. They are used for various monitoring activities and report their findings to a centralized base station. They can monitor different physical or environmental conditions, such as temperature, sound, vibrations and so on. They are used in many industrial and civilian application areas, including industrial process monitoring and control, machine health monitoring, environment and habitat monitoring. In addition to one or more sensors, each node in a sensor network is typically equipped with a radio transceiver or other wireless communications device, a small micro-controller, and an energy source, usually a battery. Typically there are two constraints here: (a) limited memory requirements and (b) conserving the battery power.

Now most sensor application involve deploying the nodes in the work-field for long periods of time, and leave them unattended. The nodes have to survive on their limited memory available, and there are no possibilities of plugging in additional memory like secondary storage. Extra storage is expensive and

the network should utilize its existing resources as effectively as possible [2]. The solution to all these problems comes in the form of efficient compression of data. We need to compress the information at each node of the network, and decompress it as we progress towards the base station. There are a number of different compression algorithms to choose from, each with its own performance benefits and tradeoffs. Memory requirements of the system decrease because compressed code and data require less space, and thus consume less resources in the network making it energy-efficient.

3 Forces

3.1 Universal Forces

Many compression techniques look to explore redundancy of data usually expressed by a compression ratio [3]. The basic redundancy mechanism explored is on the bit level called as Mechanical redundancy. Other different mechanisms include exploring the semantic content (for text compression) where techniques like LZ compression come into play. Compression techniques can also be classified on the basis of lossy and lossless compression. Compression techniques that ensure that the result of decompression is exactly the same data as before compression are known as lossless. With lossy compression, decompression will produce an approximation to the original information rather than an exact copy. These techniques exploit the nature of human perception regarding data and information. Techniques such as JPEG work on this concept of human perception to transform data into a compressed form storing only relevant information.

3.2 Implementation Forces

Based on the redundancy techniques highlighted above, many patterns remove different kinds of redundancy and depending on the compression technique there are different repercussions for accessing the compressed data. Processor and memory costs are among the foremost of considerations while implementing many of these techniques. A technique called as difference coding is considered to have the least processor and memory costs among the compression techniques. There is also tradeoff between encoding and decoding in many compression techniques. In some techniques, increasing the cost of encoding decreases the cost of decoding correspondingly. Other compression mechanisms and languages such as Java do not incur any costs of decompression. Other forces include programming cost and issues regarding random access and synchronization. Mechanisms which provide a way to access individual items within a file without reading a completed stream are helpful. The data compression ratio, expressed as the percentage of compressed data size with respect to the original data size, is a direct metric for quantifying the reduction in data quantity achieved by a compression algorithm. In the application of energy-limited systems, energy consumption is a metric that needs to be considered explicitly.

4 Implementation

One of the characteristics of sensor networks is the huge streams of data being processed either at a base station or by intermediary sensor nodes. In such cases the main question becomes how to reduce the memory consumption of large sequences of real-time event data[4]. Difference coding plays an important role here in reducing the memory consumption of data streams which are accessed sequentially and where there is significant time and financial costs in storing and transferring data. Since the data is processed offline, the onus is on reducing the programmers effort in compression-decompression operations. It has been observed that sensor data sequences are rarely random, and so the task merely becomes to represent sequences according to the differences between each event in the sequence[5]. To reduce the number of bits stored, there are several techniques such as Delta Encoding and Run Length Encoding.

Fig. 1. Figure showing a typical delta code.

Difference compression can achieve an excellent compression ratio for many kinds of sensor data. Sequential operations on the compressed data can execute almost as fast as operations on the original values. This helps in improving performance and in communicating and responding quickly. The implementation is quite easy and it does not take much extra memory. The first implementation

is of delta coding. Delta coding (or difference coding) stores differences between adjacent items, rather than the absolute values of the items themselves. Delta coding saves memory space because deltas can often be stored in smaller amounts of memory than absolute values. For example, you may be able to encode a slowly varying stream of sixteen bit values using only eight-bit delta codes. A typical delta code is represented by Figure 1. A sample delta code explaining the encoding-decoding process is shown below.

```

void delta_encode(char *buffer , int length)
{
char t = 0;
char original;
int i;
    for(i = 0; i < length; i++)
    {
        original = buffer[i];
        buffer[i] -= t;
        t = original;
    }
}

void delta_decode(char *buffer , int length)
{
char t = 0;
int i;
    for(i = 0; i < length; i++)
    {
        buffer[i] += t;
        t = buffer[i];
    }
}

```

Here the encoder takes each char in the array and replaces it by itself minus the previous(original) char. If the original array was *abcdef*, something like *a (b-a) (c-b) (d-c) (e-d) (f-e)* would be obtained. Decoding does the opposite to reconstruct it. It is useful when subsequent pieces of data are similar, such as an audio recording or something. Differences would be smaller than the absolute values themselves, so they could be compressed/stored in a smaller amount of space.

The second is of run-length encoding. Run-length encoding compresses a run of duplicated items by storing the value of the duplicated items once, followed by the length of the run. For example, we can extend the delta code above to compress runs by always following the escape code by a count byte as well as the absolute value. Runs of between 4 and 256 items can be compressed as the escape code, the absolute value of the repeated item, and the count. Runs of longer than 256 items can be stored as repeated runs of 256 characters, plus one

more run of the remainder. A typical run-length code is represented by Figure 2. A typical run-length encoding algorithm is shown below. Here given an input string *str* the count of each letter is stored in *count* for encoding purposes.

```

void run_encode(char *str , int [] count)
{
    l = strlen(str);
    for(i=0;i<l;i*=1)
    {
        j = 0;
        count[i] = 1;
        do
        {
            j++;
            if(str[i+j] == str[i])
                count[i]++;
        } while(str[i+j]==str[i]);
        if(count[i]==1)
            cout<<str[i++];
        else
        {
            i += count[i];
        }
    }
}

```

There are also other techniques such as lossy difference compression. Usually lossy difference compression is applied in cases when a sequence has negligible differences in values. In such cases they are treated as if they were a run of items with identical values. A typical lossy difference compression is shown in Figure 3.

5 Invariant

Some base stations in a sensor network need to process bulk amounts of event data coming from different sensors in the network. Base stations typically have a large amount of data to store, transmit or receive. Due to cost and space requirements many of these base stations do not have enough persistent memory to store over a long term. Sometime not enough transient memory space is needed for processing the data. In such cases adaptive compression techniques are very useful which can examine the nature of data being processed and make compression-decompression decisions. Due to the diverse nature of sensor event data and the energy-efficiency requirements of the overall network, adaptive compression algorithms can decide several parameters such as what data to discard for lossy compression and so on. The best example of an adaptive compression is that of LZ coding. LZ compression uses the data already encoded as a table to allow a compact representation of following data. LZ compression is easy to

Fig. 2. Figure showing a typical run-length code.

implement and decoding is fast and requires little extra temporary memory and works by encoding sequences of tuples.

6 Examples

There are several applications where a combination of difference compression and run length encoding comes into play in delivering a potentially useful application. A combination of both of these techniques do not yield any loss of information and a typical compression code sequence contains both the compressed value as well as the length of the sequence. The encode algorithm takes a sequence of *shorts* and the encoding function checks if the argument contains a sequence of identical values and using the run-length compression algorithm it increases the run-length count for the sequence. If the sequence is now the maximum length that can be represented, an escape code is written. If its argument is within the range of the delta coding (128 from the last value) an escape code is written if necessary, and a delta code is written. Finally, if the argument is outside the range, an escape code is written to terminate the current run length encoded sequence if necessary.

```

int SE = 0xff;
int MSL = 0xFE;

```


Fig. 3. Figure showing a typical lossy difference compression code.

```

short lS;
short rL;

void encode(short [] input)
{
    lSh = 0;
    rLe = 0;
    for (int i = 0; i < input.length; i++)
    {
        encoding(input[i]);
    }
}

```

In the decoding function if an escape code is read, a run of output values is written, and if a delta code is read, a single output is written which differs from the last output value by the delta.

```

void decode(byte [] buffer)
{
    lS = 0;
    int bR;
    while ((bR = stream.read()) != -1)

```

```

    {
        bR = bR & 0xff;
        if (bR == SE)
        {
            lS = (short) (((stream.read() & 0xff) << 8)
                + (stream.read() & 0xff));
            for (int c = stream.read(); c > 0; c--)
            {
                writeDecodedShort(lS);
            }
        }
        else
        {
            writeDecodedShort(lS += bR - 128);
        }
    }
}

```

7 Known Uses

Compression is ubiquitous and used widely. Internally, operating systems use compression in the secondary storage, and this provides a way to store more information. Compression is also used in Virtual Machines and in File Compression Tools. Compression is needed in low power devices and many recent techniques propose ways to transmit compressed information in an energy-efficient manner. This is observed in the design and development of communications protocols. Compression techniques are popular with images. The TIFF image file format uses run length-encoding to encode runs of identical pixels. The GIF and PNG formats are also based on similar principles. MPEG video compression uses a variety of techniques to express each picture as a set of differences from the previous one.

References

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